

CONTEXTUAL VARIATIONS IN LANGUAGE: EXPLORING HOW SPEECH AND WRITING ADAPT TO DIFFERENT SITUATIONS

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqola turli holatli omillarning nutq va yozma nutqda til ishlatishga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishini o'rganadi. Maqolada bu o'zgarishlarni tushuntiradigan lingvistik nazariyalar ko'rib chiqiladi va kontekst tilni qanday shakllantirishi haqida misollar keltiriladi. Ishda rasmiy va norasmiy registrlar, ijtimoiy va kasbiy kommunikatsiya, hamda madaniyatlararo omillar ko'rib chiqilib, bu omillarning tilning ohangi, lug'ati va tuzilishiga qanday ta'sir qilishi muhokama qilinadi.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется, как различные ситуационные факторы влияют на использование языка как в речи, так и в письме. Рассматриваются лингвистические теории, объясняющие эти изменения, и приводятся примеры, иллюстрирующие, как контекст формирует язык. Работа будет исследовать формальные и неформальные регистры, социальное и профессиональное общение, а также межкультурные аспекты, обсуждая, как эти факторы воздействуют на тон, словарный запас и структуру языка.

Annotation: This article investigates how different situational factors influence the way language is used in both speech and writing. It considers linguistic theories that explain these variations and provides examples that illustrate how context shapes language. The paper will explore formal and informal registers, social and professional communication, and cross-cultural considerations, discussing how such factors affect the tone, vocabulary, and structure of language.

Kalit so'zlar: Til, nutq, dialektlar, muloqot, kontekst, matn, vaziyat, madaniyatlararo tushunish, ijtimoiy me'yorlar va boshqalar.

Ключевые слова: Язык, речь, диалекты, общение, контекст, текст, ситуация, межкультурное понимание, социальные нормы и др.

Keywords: Language, speech, dialects, communication, context, text, situation, cross-cultural understanding, social norms and etc.

Language can change depending on the social context of its speakers, and in different situations and for various purposes; speakers may use different language varieties. English, one of the most widely spoken languages in the world, is no exception. However, many people remain unaware of the social and regional dialects and diverse varieties of English used globally. Understanding these variations is crucial for all members of society, particularly those in higher education. Language is not static; it is highly adaptable, reflecting the social environment in which it is used. The way we communicate—whether spoken or written—changes based on the situation, audience, purpose, and social norms. Understanding these contextual variations is crucial for linguists, educators, and communicators to craft appropriate messages and facilitate comprehension. This paper aims to outline key factors influencing linguistic adaptations and provide examples illustrating how speech and writing respond to diverse contexts.

Informal English, characterized by the use of abbreviations and contractions, is more common in society than formal English. According to Barzan and Heydari (2019), “Lingua Franca is defined as a language which is used habitually by people whose mother tongues are different in order to facilitate communication. They are not only spoken differently in different places, but individual speakers varied widely in their ability to use language.”⁹ This indicates that a lingua franca, such as English, serves as a trade, contact, or international language. When using language in a dialect or specific variety, it is important to consider not just what to say but how to say it. Effective communication depends on matching language to the audience, purpose, and context, even when a sentence is lexically and grammatically correct.

As Hutson (1994) stated, “You are what you speak, how you speak it.” This highlights how language reflects not only the speaker's intent but also the broader

⁹ Hasan, R. (2001). “Wherefore context? The place of context in the system and process of language”. In *Grammar and Discourse: Proceedings of the International Conference on Discourse Analysis*, ed. R. Shaozeng, W. Guthrie, and I.I.R. Fong, 1–21. Macau: Publication Centre, University of Macau.

social conditions As Hasan (2001) mentioned that texts do not come into being in isolation from their contexts. The very fact that a text is an instance of social meaning “presupposes” some kind of social context (cf. Hasan 2001), and social contexts, when “filtered” through language contain three features:

1. The nature of the social process.
2. The nature of the relationship between the interactants.
3. The nature of the code for message transmission (Hasan, 1981).¹⁰

These elements form what Hasan calls the “context of situation” and these three features are not only description of situation, but also, they are so important to the meaning expressed through the language that used within a given situation.

In addition, before speak and write our opinion, we must think what words, tone which we choose for a certain situation is appropriate or not. It is very essential to choose appropriate language for a particular context then we use it when we write and speak. Dr Knoeferle mentioned that context is important in language comprehension, but context effects are variable, and some others are stronger than others.¹¹ Language without context cannot be so important reference points and not as effective in communicating what we want to say or write.

From a teaching perspective, the use of real-life situations, relevant topics, and meaningful themes can help students grasp the importance of context in language use. Educators must highlight how language varies across formal and informal settings, thereby equipping learners to communicate effectively in diverse situations.

Conclusion

Language is not static; it adapts to the social and situational contexts in which it is used. Understanding these variations is essential for effective communication and is especially relevant for individuals in higher education. By recognizing the influence of audience, purpose, and social conditions, we can better navigate the complexities of human interaction, whether in speech or writing. Language is a dynamic tool that molds itself to different communicative contexts. Recognizing and

¹⁰ Hasan, R. (1981). “What’s going on: A dynamic view of context in language”. In *The seventh LACUS forum 1980*, ed. J.E. Copeland and P.W. Davis, 106–121. Columbia: Hornbeam Press.

¹¹ Knoeferle, P. (2020). “How context influences language processing and comprehension”. *Research OUTREACH*, 114. Available at: <https://researchoutreach.org/articles/how-context-influences-language-processing-comprehension/>

understanding these variations not only enhances communication effectiveness but also helps in promoting cross-cultural understanding. This awareness is essential for linguists, educators, and anyone engaged in fields requiring effective communication.

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